

From camera trap to GBIF

Project report for the NLBIF project “Van cameraval tot GBIF”

Project information

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Partner	Wageningen University & Research (WUR)
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Summary

Camera trapping has become one of the most important technologies in conservation and ecological research and is now a well-established, non-invasive method for collecting field data on animal abundance, distribution, behaviour, temporal activity and space use. To facilitate researchers in managing camera-trap projects and annotating and storing camera trap images, Wageningen University & Research (WUR) and the Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO) develop and maintain the platform Agouti. In the NLBIF-funded project “Van cameraval tot GBIF” (2019-2021), we developed tools and formats to facilitate sharing and archiving this type of data.

The initially suggested Camera Trap Metadata Standard (CTMS) turned out to be insufficient and no longer maintained as a data exchange format. We therefore partnered with the Open Science Conservation Fund (creators of TRAPPER) to develop a new data exchange format: **Camera Trap Data Package (Camtrap DP)**. This format is now hosted by Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG), reaching a stable release and gaining wider support. We updated Agouti so that users can export their data in this standardized format with a single click.

Agouti now also serves public images, and allows to hide images containing humans to comply with privacy laws.

To demonstrate the Camtrap DP format, we published an [open dataset](#) in this format on Zenodo, containing over 1.1 million images and 61.000 annotations. We also created a conversion script from Camtrap DP to Darwin Core, which expresses the animal observations and associated images into an Occurrence Core and Simple Multimedia Extension. This conversion was used to publish the Zenodo dataset as a [new dataset to GBIF](#). Both datasets are licensed under a CC0 waiver. The software code, dataset and especially the Camtrap DP data exchange format have the potential to be widely used beyond Agouti. Overall, the project has made a substantial contribution to the standardized exchange of camera trap data, both within the camera trapping and GBIF community, and we thank NLBIF for the financial support.

Project results

New data exchange format for camera trap data

One of the objectives was to use a data standard for Agouti exports. The project proposal suggested the Camera Trap Metadata Standard (CTMS), described in Forrester et al. (2016, <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.4.e10197>). We did however not adopt this format because it lacks some important terms and relations, it is not maintained or versioned, and it does not seem to be adopted. Looking for alternatives, we started collaborating with Jakub Bubnicki (Open Science Conservation Fund) who had initiated a data export format for [TRAPPER](#), another camera trap data management system. Our collaboration was later joined by Ben Norton (North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences) and other members of the camera trapping community.

This collaboration resulted in **Camera Trap Data Package (Camtrap DP)**, a data exchange format for camera trap data. It captures all relevant information about a camera trapping project, its deployments, associated multimedia and observations¹. Rather than starting from scratch, Camtrap DP is built on [Frictionless Standards](#), a set of generic specifications to describe and package (tabular) data and metadata. Camtrap DP extends these with specific requirements and constraints for camera trap data. By building on this existing framework, users can make use of existing [open source software](#) to read and validate Camtrap DP formatted data. Validation especially is useful to automatically inspect if provided data meets the requirements set forth by Camtrap DP, before analysing or integrating these.

Camtrap DP is versioned on GitHub and automatically generated from the source files as a website (Figure 1). It is now managed by the [Machine Observations Interest Group](#) of Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) and developed publicly, soliciting community

¹ These observations not only include animal identifications, but also annotations indicating a sequence of images is blank or a camera setup. This wider scope and the need for specific attributes (camera setup, bait use, sequences, AI annotations) is why Darwin Core (Archive) is not a suitable data exchange format to capture all information about a camera trap project.

feedback for every change. It is supported by the major camera trap data management systems Agouti, TRAPPER, [eMammal](#) and [Wildlife Insights](#) and reaching its first stable version.

Camera Trap Data Package (or **Camtrap DP** for short) is a community developed data exchange format for camera trap data. A Camtrap DP is a **Frictionless Data Package** that consists of:

File	Description
<code>datapackage.json</code>	Metadata regarding the data package and camera trap project.
<code>deployments.csv</code>	Table with camera trap deployments .
<code>multimedia.csv</code>	Table with multimedia files captured by the camera traps.
<code>observations.csv</code>	Table with observations based on the multimedia files.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the Camtrap DP website at <https://tdwg.github.io/camtrap-dp/>

New features in Agouti

We developed or extended several key functionalities in Agouti.

Project owners can now **download all relevant data** for their project in the Camtrap DP format (version 0.1.4). This can be done with a single click, after which a zip file is prepared. It includes essentially all relevant data stored for a project in Agouti, including project properties, associated organization and collaborators, geographic/temporal/taxonomic scope, deployments, multimedia (URLs) and all annotations (species identifications and sequences marked as blank or camera setup). It also includes the identifier and timestamp of the generated file for future reference. The format is documented on the Camtrap DP website. – *1a. Implementatie CTMS views op database, 1b. Aanpassen API endpoints, 1d. Front-end ontwikkeling procedure download (asynchroon), 4b. Documentatie data package opbouw*²

² All project objectives as described in the proposal (in Dutch) are referenced as small italic text in the relevant project results.

Due to their size and volume, multimedia files are not included in exports. Rather, Wageningen University & Research (WUR) has taken on the responsibility to **archive and serve all Agouti images** intended for public use. Files are now served via a multimedia API using stable URLs (e.g. <https://multimedia.agouti.eu/assets/42ee7b66-4660-4f53-96f1-b6ad4cbfe91a/file>). This feature not only increases export speed, but also relieves users from having to move and archive images themselves (e.g. on Zenodo). – 1c. Implementatie dump foto's voor geselecteerd project

In compliance with **GDPR**, Agouti users can opt out of having their name included in exports (Figure 2) and in a future release, multimedia containing humans will not be served by the multimedia API.

Figure 2: Screenshot of Agouti user settings, where users can opt to be anonymous in exports.

We decided not to require open data publication as a condition to use Agouti. This freedom attracts more users to Agouti and as a result, their camera trap data are managed better. We did however make it significantly easier to publish and archive camera trap data following FAIR principles. Images are now archived by Wageningen University & Research (WUR). Project owners will be able to opt whether these can be served publicly. By adopting Camtrap DP as (the only) export format, data from Agouti are highly interoperable with data originating from other commonly used camera trap data management systems. An export always contains all data from a project, so it is the perfect unit to deposit as a dataset on e.g. Zenodo, thus meeting the other FAIR principles. Work on the Camtrap DP format has postponed describing *how* to deposit data on Zenodo, but an example dataset exists (see further) and a static documentation website has been created and will be launched by the end of 2021. – 3a. Opname open data publicatie voorwaarden in Terms of Service, 3b. Ontwikkeling project settings front-end, 4a. Opzetten static documentatie website, 4b. Documentatie publicatie Zenodo

Open and FAIR dataset on Zenodo

We published Cartuyvels et al. (2021a, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4893244>) as the **first open camera trap dataset using the Camtrap DP format**. It comprises all data from an active project and currently contains over 1.1 million images (links) and 61.000 annotations. The dataset was created by uploading the 4 files of a Camtrap DP/Agouti export:

`datapackage.json`, `deployments.csv`, `multimedia.csv` and `observations.csv` on Zenodo. The files were uploaded as is, with the exception of `deployments.csv`, where the coordinates were rounded to 3 decimals (maximum 111m) to prevent camera trap theft. We documented the dataset with metadata (authors, background, structure and funding acknowledgements) and released it under a Creative Commons Zero (CC0) waiver. – 2a. Uitwerken data publicatie naar Zenodo

The Frictionless Data Package structure of the dataset allows users to get access to all the data by loading a single small file: the `datapackage.json` file. This file references and describes all other files, allowing the user to only load data when necessary. To help users even further, we developed an **R package** to read data from *any* Frictionless Data package in two easy steps. Since Camtrap DPs are Frictionless Data Packages, anyone can use the [R package](#) to read data from the dataset (Figure 3).

```
# devtools::install_github("inbo/datapackage")
library(datapackage)

# Read datapackage.json file from Zenodo
dp <- read_package("https://zenodo.org/record/4893244/files/datapackage.json")
#> Please make sure you have the right to access data from this Data Package for your proposed use.
#> Follow applicable norms or requirements to credit the dataset and its authors.
#> For more information, see https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4893244

# List resource names
dp$resource_names
#> [1] "deployments" "multimedia" "observations"

# Read data from "observations", using the metadata to set column data types
observations <- read_resource(dp, "observations")
nrow(observations)
#> [1] 61823
head(observations)
#> # A tibble: 6 x 20
#>   observation_id deployment_id sequence_id multimedia_id timestamp
#>   <chr>          <chr>          <chr>          <chr>          <dtm>
#> 1 e0b65f26-f9db-4... 005eaf17-3197... e0b65f26-f9... <NA>          2020-10-08 07:51:23
#> 2 a8a7c06c-3ab4-4... 005eaf17-3197... a8a7c06c-3a... <NA>          2020-10-09 00:49:00
#> 3 ffa9e490-5c56-4... 005eaf17-3197... ffa9e490-5c... <NA>          2020-10-09 02:10:54
#> 4 b02db2e1-fefa-4... 005eaf17-3197... b02db2e1-fe... <NA>          2020-10-09 04:25:39
#> 5 169911cb-8e8d-4... 005eaf17-3197... 169911cb-8e... <NA>          2020-10-09 04:34:35
#> 6 68d7459c-840e-4... 005eaf17-3197... 68d7459c-84... <NA>          2020-10-09 16:40:32
#> # ... with 15 more variables: observation_type <fct>, sensor_method <fct>,
#> #   camera_setup <lgl>, scientific_name <chr>, taxon_id <chr>, count <dbl>,
#> #   age <fct>, sex <fct>, behaviour <chr>, individual_id <chr>,
#> #   classification_method <fct>, classified_by <chr>,
#> #   classification_timestamp <dtm>, classification_confidence <dbl>,
#> #   comments <chr>
```

Figure 3: Code to showcase how data from the dataset on Zenodo can easily be loaded into an R data frame with the newly developed R package “datapackage”.

Transformation to Darwin Core

Camtrap DP datasets capture all relevant information about a camera trap project, but cannot be harvested directly by GBIF (as of now). A dataset therefore needs to be transformed to Darwin Core first. We have done this in two steps: a generic and dataset-specific one. – 2b.

Ontwikkeling tool om CTMS naar DwC om te zetten, 4c. Documentatie conversie CTMS naar DwC

The **generic step** is documented in the [dwc-for-biologging](#) GitHub repository and can be used for any Camtrap DP dataset. It was reviewed by the members of the TDWG Machine Observations Interest Group and maps Camtrap DP source data to Darwin Core as an Occurrence core and a Simple Multimedia extension. This is also the format recommended by [Cadman & González-Talaván \(2014\) Publishing Camera Trap Data: A Best Practice Guide](#) (see [template file](#)). Although this does not allow capturing the deployment date range, it does allow sharing all relevant information about the source of the observations (i.e. the images), which is considered more worthwhile for primary occurrence data (see also [this discussion](#)). The code to do this consists of 2 SQL queries:

- [dwc_occurrence.sql](#): This query transforms Camtrap DP observation data to a Darwin Core Occurrence core (Machine Observations). This allows linking occurrences to images in a Multimedia extension, which would not be possible if there already was an Event core. As a result, deployment start/end information is not included. However, by including an eventID in the Occurrence core for each deployment, GBIF will present occurrences grouped by [deployment](#).
- [dwc_multimedia.sql](#): This query transforms Camtrap DP multimedia data to a Darwin Core Simple Multimedia extension. Sets of images will appear multiple times if these are used for multiple occurrences.

The **dataset-specific step** is documented in the INBO [mica-occurrences](#) GitHub repository. It loads the two files from the generic step in R and adds fields that are specific to that dataset (e.g. datasetName, license, rightsHolder). These files were then uploaded to the [INBO IPT](#), documented with metadata, and registered with GBIF.

The transformation step to GBIF is not complicated, but can be a burden for data publishers. We hope to partly facilitate this process in the NLBIF project [MOVE2GBIF](#), where we will develop tools that can be used for Camtrap DP datasets as well. Eventually, we hope that the transformation steps can be generic and community-approved so that GBIF can directly harvest Camtrap DP datasets from Zenodo.

Open and FAIR dataset on GBIF

Cartuyvels et al. (2021b, <https://doi.org/10.15468/5tb6ze>) is the resulting **dataset on GBIF**. The dataset contains camera trap observations of muskrat and coypu, as well as many other observed species, currently amounting to close to 28.000 observations and 454.000 images. – 2c. Testen van data publicatie flow naar GBIF

We documented the dataset with extensive metadata. The Description explains that the dataset only contains the animal observations of the source dataset on Zenodo. Both datasets reference each other. The [Methodology](#) section lists all the (transformation) steps from field to Agouti to Zenodo to GBIF. All funders, including NLBIF, are acknowledged.

The dataset is permanently published under a Creative Commons Zero (CC0) waiver and we plan to update it regularly with new data.